

METHODS OF TEACHING THE MORPHOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS NON-LINGUISTIC DIRECTIONS

Saidova Moxira Rasulevna

Candidate of Philology, Associate Professor of the Department of Russian Linguistics, Faculty
of Philology, Bukhara State University

Avezova Dilovar Salimovna

Lecturer at the Department of Russian Linguistics, Faculty of Philology, Bukhara State
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7517111>

Abstract. *In the university methodology of teaching the Russian language, the study of morphology is always a kind of stumbling block, especially for students of non-linguistic undergraduate areas. On the one hand, in order to master grammatical concepts, a certain level of development of abstract thinking is necessary, which is created in the learning process and requires special exercises aimed at developing certain mental skills and a complex of linguistic representations. On the other hand, the process of forming concepts is also the process of mastering by students such mental operations as analysis and synthesis, comparison, generalization and systematization, abstraction and concretization.*

Keywords: *morphology, university teaching, nominal parts of speech and verb, spelling skills, grammatical and lexical meaning of the word.*

Morphology is a branch of grammar that studies the forms of words and the totality of the forms of words in a language. The tasks of morphology include the definition of the word as a special linguistic object and the description of its internal structure.

The objectives of teaching morphology in the course "Russian language" are:

- to systematize students' knowledge about parts of speech; form the concept of the main grammatical categories of parts of speech;
- to give an idea of the inseparable connection of lexical and grammatical meanings in separate parts of speech;
- to identify the specifics of the formation of nominal parts of speech and the verb;
- to acquaint students with the functioning of various parts of speech in speech;
- to develop spelling skills, taking into account the partial belonging of words.

When studying parts of speech, a functional-semantic approach is carried out. The essence of this approach is to show the functions of linguistic phenomena in language and speech. The functional-semantic approach implies a close relationship between the grammatical form and the meaning, showing the contexts in which the meaning of the units of the language is realized, their contextual indicators, the patterns of functioning of grammatical forms and structures in certain types of speech.

The functional criterion involves an assessment of the functions that words of a given class perform in a sentence, for example: the most characteristic functions of a noun are the functions of the subject and object; the only function performed in the sentence by the verb in the

personal form is the function of the predicate; the adjective is characterized by the function of definition; for an adverb it is a function of circumstance.

The tradition of distinguishing between the terms school and scientific (academic, university) grammar has firmly entrenched in the methodology of teaching the Russian language. These two concepts very often diverge not only in scope, but also in essence. Some researchers believe that there can be no "school" and "scientific" theory: a school theory should be a "school scientific theory". Others justify different approaches to many issues by the fact that the goals and objectives of language learning at school and university do not always coincide. The main task of university studies is to understand the essence of language as a special social phenomenon, the features of its structure and functioning.

Teaching at the university is much more focused on the cognitive value of the Russian language as an academic subject. The tasks of teaching the Russian language at school are focused on practical value.

The main difficulties that arise in the study of parts of speech include the following:

The difference between students of parts of speech in the case of the transition of words from one part of speech to another (words like dining room, manager, sideways, past, etc.);

Students mixing the concepts of "member of a sentence" and "part of speech" (errors of this kind persist for a very long time);

The difference in outwardly similar forms (dative and prepositional cases of feminine nouns with endings -е and -и: country, water, line, notebook, salt; comparative degree of adjective and adverb: was more beautiful and made more beautiful, etc.);

The difference in outwardly similar forms (dative and prepositional cases of feminine nouns with endings -е and -и: country, water, line, notebook, salt; comparative degree of adjective and adverb: was more beautiful and made more beautiful, etc.);

When studying the name of an adjective, students of non-linguistic faculties find it difficult to agree on an adjective with a noun;

Numerals are especially difficult when used in oral speech. In written speech, numerals are used in business papers, therefore, in the classroom, special attention should be paid to the declension of numerals, while using them with nouns;

Difficulties arise in delimiting the categories of pronouns and in determining their initial form;

The main difficulty in mastering the verb is connected with the study of the category of aspect, which is not in the Uzbek language;

When studying participles and gerunds, a semantic criterion is very important - the recognition of participles and gerunds. Students find it difficult to designate participial and participle turns in writing. The difficulty arises in the distinction between H - HH and in the spelling of NOT with participles.

In the course of morphology, students should acquire the following skills:

1. Be able to ask a grammatical question to the word.
2. Determine the grammatical affiliation of the word.
4. Distinguish between the grammatical and lexical meaning of the word.
5. Decline and conjugate words in accordance with grammatical norms.
6. Find the studied grammatical phenomena in the phrase, sentence and text.
7. Make a morphological analysis of words of different parts of speech, etc.

According to A. M. Smolkin, when solving difficult problems of morphology, three main groups of methods are used: 1) verbal; 2) visual; 3) practical.

Verbal (theoretical) methods include: storytelling, explanation, explanation, instruction, commenting, task, indication, conversation, analysis, analysis.

Thanks to the word, you can convey the necessary knowledge, activate and deepen perception, set a task and formulate the attitude of students towards it, you can manage the process of completing the task, analyze and evaluate the results, correct the progress of the task, comment on its implementation.

When solving difficult questions of morphology, the word can be used and expressed in the form:

- didactic story, conversation, discussion;
- instructions (explanation of the task, the rules for their implementation);
- accompanying explanation (concise commentary and remarks);
- assessments (method of current correction of actions or their results);
- verbal report and mutual explanation.

Visual (sensory) methods are diverse and aimed at activating sensory processes in students. First of all, these include: demonstration of exercises or their elements by the teacher. Auxiliary visual methods include: demonstration of posters with the rules for performing exercises, schemes (algorithm) for performing an exercise, the use of demonstration boards (for example, an interactive whiteboard), tablets, information technology.

It should be borne in mind that visual perception for some students "visuals" is much stronger than verbal explanation. Therefore, the implementation of the exercise by the teacher on the board, visual aids available to students help them form the correct ideas.

Orientation methods are of some importance (for example, landmarks in parsing a word by composition, etc.).

Visualization is provided through sensory methods. This is not only visual, but also auditory perception. Touch methods can be implemented in the form:

- showing the performance of tasks or exercises;
- demonstration of visual aids;
- computer demonstrations (viewing special educational videos).

Practical methods are based on the active cognitive activity of students. For example, performing exercises within the time limit - 10 or 15 minutes in a Russian lesson; performing exercises with the help of visual aids (textbook, workbook); performing well-known, learning exercises.

When solving difficult questions of morphology, dictations, essays, presentation, text copying, sentence analysis and morphological analysis of the word can be used.

Educational and search tasks are divided into two groups according to the sources of interest: problem tasks and tasks with entertaining components. Problem tasks are tasks with identification and explanatory functions. "The essence of problematic assignments lies in the teacher creating a problematic situation, in posing such a question that would become a problem for students, a task.

Such questions involve several answers - guesswork, and the student must find the key to solving this problem and choose only one correct answer. Finding the right way to solve the problem activates the mental activity of students.

Game technologies are one of the ways to increase the motivation to study the Russian language at a university, the formation of cognitive interest, allows you to overcome the barrier of uncertainty, develops oral and written speech among students. In the game, the abilities of a person, and a student in particular, are manifested especially fully and sometimes unexpectedly. The game always involves making a decision - what to do, what to say, how to win?

The desire to solve these questions sharpens the mental activity of students. It is feasible even for those who are lagging behind. Moreover, a student who is weak in language training can become the first in the game: resourcefulness and ingenuity here are sometimes more important than knowledge of the subject. A sense of equality, an atmosphere of enthusiasm and joy, a sense of the feasibility of tasks - all this enables students to overcome shyness that prevents them from freely using the words of a foreign language in speech and has a beneficial effect on learning outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Verbitsky A.A. Active learning in higher education: contextual approach.: method. allowance. - Moscow: Higher School, 1991. - 207 p.
2. Cough N.N. Activity approach in advanced training: active teaching methods. - Minsk: Institute for Advanced Studies and Retraining of Managers and Education Specialists, 1994.
3. Maksimov L. Yu. Professionalization of teaching the Russian language at the Pedagogical Institute // ПЯИИ. 1992. No. 4.
4. Malakhovskiy V.A. Methodology of the Russian language. - Moscow, 2005.
5. Passov E. I. The Russian Word in Methodology as a Way to the World of the Russian Word, or Does Methodology Have a Future? St. Petersburg: MIRS, 2008.
6. Psychological dictionary. / Ed. A.V. Petrovsky, M.G. Yaroshevsky. – M.: Logos, 2015.
7. Smolkin A.M. Methods of active learning: scientific. - method. allowance. - Moscow: Higher School, 1991.
8. Talyzina N. F. Management of the process of mastering knowledge: textbook. method. allowance. - M.: Higher school, 1975.
9. Uspensky M. B. The course of the modern Russian language in a pedagogical university: textbook. Moscow: publishing house of the Moscow Psychological and Social Institute, 2004.
10. Shmatkov E.V. Vocational training methodology: method. allowance. - Kharkov, 2002.